

**INTENTION TO STAY AMONG EMPLOYEES AND THEIR WORK
ENGAGEMENT IN THE BUSINESS PROCESS OUTSOURCING (BPO)
COMPANIES**

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ABSTRACT

The study aims to determine which domain of intention to stay among employees best predicts work engagement among BPO employees in Davao City. This study used quantitative non-experimental research design using correlation method to 100 call center agents as participants working in the BPO companies. Adapted questionnaires were used in the gathering of data. The statistical tools used in data analysis were Mean, Pearson-r and linear regression. Findings showed that the level of intention to stay among employees was high as well as their work engagement. There was a significant relationship between intention to stay among employees and their work engagement. There was significant influence of intention to stay among employees on their work engagement. Person organization fit as domain of intention to stay best predict work engagement of employees. Regression equation was developed to predict work engagement.

Keywords:

Intention to stay, work engagement, BPO companies, Davao City, Philippines

INTRODUCTION

The country has witnessed the rise of another industry known as Business Process Outsourcing or BPO. Under the BPO system, corporation's farm out routine or non-core office functions to developing countries BPO companies or call centers offer round the clock services that include the handling of complaints and inquiries of customers abroad, providing them with technical support via the internet, and rendering medical and legal transcription services (Lomibao, 2007).

Call center agents comprises the largest Business Process Outsourcing workers in country today. The BPO sector is a contemporary work setting in the Philippines, with a large and relatively young workforce. The work of a customer service representative is seen as one of the ten most stressful jobs in the current world economy (Holdsworth, 2003). There is a concern that the demands of the work environment in call center may contribute to stress levels and psychological vulnerability among employees (Visser and Rothmann, 2008).

FRAMEWORK

Intention to stay mirrors the employee's level of commitment to his organization and the willingness to remain employed (Hewitt, 2004). Thus, employee intention to stay or remain with an organization is very significant for the progress and success of the organization. From modern human resource perspective, human capital is the most valuable assets for the organizations (Mello, 2011; Honore, 2009). The managers need to recognize the value of their employees by encouraging them to remain for their resource talent to be used, and also discourage them from looking elsewhere for better opportunities. This cannot be argued as a result of other

resource no matter their significance depends on the knowledge of employee in a very extent (Eketu & Edeh, 2015).

Work engagement, the discretionary attachment of oneself with one's role, represents quality of attachment in terms of three components namely vigor, dedication and absorption and quantity of attachment by the value its components hold (Harju et al. 2016, Schaufeli et al. 2002).

Modern organizations need energetic and dedicated employees: people who are engaged with their work. These organizations expect proactivity, initiative and responsibility for personal development from their employees (Bakker, 2010). A number of research studies have found work engagement to be positively associated with intent to remain with one's organization (Harter et al. 2002, Schaufeli and Bakker 2004). The greater the employee's engagement in the company, the greater the intention to stay (Fernandes & Balu, 2018).

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study aims to determine which domain of intention to stay among employees best predicts the work engagement in the BPO companies. Specifically, the study aims to determine the level of intention to stay among employees and their work engagement. Further, it also aims to determine the relationship between intention to stay among employees and their work engagement.

METHODOLOGY

This study used quantitative non-experimental research design using correlation method to 100 call center agents as participants working in the BPO companies. Adapted questionnaires from the studies on turnover intention (Choong et al., 2013) were used in the gathering of data. Mean, Pearson-r and linear regression were the statistical tools used in the data analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the analysis and interpretation of gathered data. Disclosed in Table 1 the level of intention to stay among employees in the BPO companies and it is of high level with the overall mean rating of 3.84. This means that the BPO employees often intend to stay in their companies. Moreover, they showed a high level of organizational commitment with a mean of 4.12, which means that their intention to stay is highly determined by their commitment to stay in the organization. This finding affirms with the proposition of Hewitt (2004) that intention to stay in the organization is the mirror of employee's level of commitment and the willingness to remain employed.

Table 1: Level of Intention to Stay Among Employees in the BPO Companies

Intention to Stay	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Organizational Commitment	.68	4.12	High
Job Stress	.70	3.51	High
Person Organization Fit	.67	3.98	High
Compensation and Benefits Packages	.86	3.63	High
Overall	.53	3.84	High

Presented in Table 2 shows the high level of work engagement of employees in the BPO companies with the mean rating of 3.80. In relation to vigor, dedication and absorption as indicators, dedication has the highest mean of 4.06 with a descriptive level of high. Vigor and absorption garnered 3.78 and 3.56 respectively. This means that BPO employees often manifest work engagement. This finding corroborate with the concept of Harju et al. (2016), Schaufeli et al. (2002) that work engagement, the discretionary attachment of oneself with one's role, represents quality of attachment in terms of three components namely vigor, dedication and absorption and quantity of attachment by the value its components hold.

Table 2: Level of Work Engagement of Employees in the BPO Companies

Work Engagement	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Vigor	.85	3.78	High
Dedication	.77	4.06	High
Absorption	.78	3.56	High
Overall	.68	3.80	High

Presented in Table 3 is the significant relationship between intention to stay among employees and their work engagement in the BPO companies. As revealed, the R-value of .506 and the p-value of .000 is lesser than .05 level of significance. All indicators of intention to stay among employees significantly related to their work engagement. This implies that work engagement among employees is dependent on their intention to stay. Further, intention to stay among employees is directly related to their work engagement. This finding affirms with the proposition of Fernandes & Balu (2018) that the greater the employee's engagement in the company, the greater the intention to stay.

Table 3: Significant Relationship Between Intention to Stay and Work Engagement of Employees in BPO Companies

Intention to Stay	Work Engagement			
	Vigor	Dedication	Absorption	Overall
Organizational Commitment	.314**	.414**	.363**	.431**
Job Stress	.151	.179	.386**	.280**
Person Organization Fit	.429**	.476**	.292**	.471**
Compensation and Benefits Package	.169	.324**	.360**	.335**
Overall	.348** (.000)	.468** (.000)	.472** (.000)	.506** (.000)

**Significant at .01

*Significant at .05

Presented in Table 4 is the significant influence of intention to stay among employees on their work engagement. It shows that intention to stay has a significant influence on the level of work engagement among employees as shown in the F value of 9.874 and a p – value of .000 which is lesser than the .05 level of significance. The R square value of 29.4% shows the percentage of influence of intention to stay to work engagement. The variance of 70.6% is attributed to other factors not covered in the study. Person organization fit as domain of intention to stay best predict work engagement of BPO employees. Regression equation was developed to predict work engagement. This finding affirms with the proposition of Harter et al. (2002), Schaufeli and Bakker (2004) that work engagement is positively associated with intent to remain with one's organization.

Table 4 Significant Influence of Intention to Stay on the Work Engagement of BPO Employees

Intention to Stay	Work Engagement		
	Beta (β)	t Value	P Value
Organizational Commitment	.261	2.353	.021
Job Stress	.143	1.636	.105
Person Organization Fit	.321	2.861	.005
Compensation and Benefits Package	-.023	-.243	.808
Rsquare	.294 or 29.4%		
F-Value	9.874		
P- Value	.000		

Regression Equation,

$$Y = 1.031 + .261X_1 + .143X_2 + .321X_3 + -.023X_4$$

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the researchers concluded that the level of intention to stay among employees was high as well as their work engagement. There was a significant relationship between intention to stay among employees and their work engagement. It was also concluded that there was a significant influence of intention to stay among employees on their work engagement. Person organization fit as domain of intention to stay best predict work engagement of employees. Regression equation was developed to predict work engagement.

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